

Environmental assessment of energy storage systems and critical raw materials: life cycle assessment of lithium production

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Context and objective

- Our society relies on **metals** for sustainable energy storage systems (e.g., batteries). **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** has become a prominent tool for quantifying environmental burdens associated with different metal production pathways, enabling the implementation of **mitigation strategies**.
- In this context, this study reviewed existing LCAs of **battery-grade lithium production** from diverse sources and extraction pathways. The aim was to provide a comprehensive assessment of the current environmental footprint of lithium production routes from primary sources, highlighting potential limitations of existing practices.

Methods and materials

Following the standardized LCA methodology as per ISO 14000 series, with a **cradle-to-gate system boundary** (extraction, processing, refining), the environmental impacts of lithium products (e.g. Li_2CO_3) from Spodumene, continental brine, and geothermal brine sources are examined, building on existing literature background studies and databases.

Figure 1. Global production and market overview of lithium, where EoL-RIR: End-of-Life Recycling-Input-Rates, RoW: Rest of the World. Building on data from [1,2,3,4]

Results

Figure 2 Global warming potential (GWP) impacts assessment [4-10]

Figure 3. Global lithium production from primary sources for existing LCA, with production share data retrieved from S&P Global Market Intelligence

Key takeaways

- Currently available LCAs cover 54% of global production sites geographically, with the remaining production sites either lacking publicly available LCA studies or being covered through parametric and simulation-based LCA approaches
- Geothermal brine, a potential future source, lacks primary data LCAs due to the absence of commercial activity from this source to date.
- Aggregation of inventory data remains a key limitation for in-depth analysis due to confidentiality issues. Key challenges include impact allocation, data access, and system boundaries.
- GWP ranges from 10-20.4 kg CO₂ eq/kg Li₂CO₃ (ore) to 2.1-3.4 kg CO₂ eq/kg Li₂CO₃ (brine), based on the LCA studies using primary data within this assessment
- Across the studies reviewed, energy inputs and chemical additives (e.g., sodium carbonate and sodium hydroxide) emerge as key drivers of environmental impact

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